

Glycine functionalized silica is an effective adsorbent for cobalt(II) and nickel(II) recovery

Jędrzej Piątek,^a Caspar N. de Bruin-Dickason,^a Aleksander Jaworski,^a Tetyana Budnyak^{a,*} and Adam Slabon^{a,*}

^a Department of Materials and Environmental Chemistry, Stockholm University, 106 91 Stockholm, Sweden

E-mail addresses: adam.slabon@mmk.su.se (A. Slabon), tetyana.budnyak@mmk.su.se (T. Budnyak)

Graphical abstract

Abstract

We disclose that glycine functionalized silica particles ($\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$) are highly effective sorbents for the removal of Co(II) and Ni(II) ions from aqueous solution. $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ can be prepared from commercial silica gel in a high yielding two step synthesis, and features a glycine concentration of $0.63 \text{ mmol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ ($27 \text{ mmol}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$). This material can recover up to $2.81 \text{ mmol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ of Co(II) ions or $3.02 \text{ mmol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ of Ni(II) ions from aqueous solution, a capacity which is tenfold higher than unmodified silica and comparable to the best performing sorbents reported in the literature. These sorption capacities are superstoichiometric in relation to the concentration of glycine on the surface. Sorption of cobalt(II) was improved by addition of ammonia to leaching solutions to give rise to more readily absorbed cobalt amine complexes. Regeneration of sorbent was investigated by desorption of adsorbed metals under mildly acidic solutions, and efficient desorption was noted for both metals. To probe the mechanism of sorption, a thorough characterization campaign involving TGA, FTIR, nitrogen adsorption/desorption, SEM, solid state NMR, solid state UV-Vis-NIR, $-\text{COOH}$ titration and $\text{pH}_{\text{pzc}} - \text{pH}$ drift methods was undertaken. Our mechanistic study indicated that the adsorption was mediated by electrostatic interaction. On the basis of its adsorption/desorption efficiency and inexpensive and green synthesis, $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ is a promising candidate for applications such as environmental remediation or recovery of valuable metals from E-waste.

Keywords: adsorption, wastewater treatment, metal recovery, surface functionalization

1. Introduction

The global scale of electronic waste (e-waste) production today exceeds 50 million metric tons per year [1]. The majority of this waste is not recycled, and instead is disposed of in landfills in developing nations. Heavy metal residues ubiquitous in e-waste landfills leach into soil and waterways, with deleterious consequences for the health of local communities. The scale of electronic waste production also presents an economic opportunity with respect to mineral recovery. E-waste is dense in valuable metallic components, and the total value of minerals discarded in e-waste is estimated to be over \$62.5 bn USD/year [2].

Sorbent chemistry offers solutions for the remediation contaminated waterways, and can contribute towards green methods for efficient recycling of valuable minerals from bulk e-waste. In general, adsorption is preferable to alternatives such as chemical precipitation, manual filtration and reverse osmosis due to the low engineering footprint of sorbent systems and minimal use of bulk chemicals required for contaminant removal which can be accomplished at neutral pH [3–12]. An effective green sorbent must have a high capacity for the contaminant of interest and be prepared by a scale-able and cheap process with a minimal environmental footprint [13].

Functionalised silica materials are an emerging family of effective green sorbents. Silica is an abundant material with low environmental toxicity. It features a negative surface charge above pH 2, allowing for strong adsorption of cations under neutral conditions, and subsequent release of adsorbates in moderately acidic washes. The introduction of functional groups can tune the adsorptive chemistry of silica materials towards a gamut of cationic substrates. Effective silica based sorbent materials have been developed for the adsorption of dyes [14], drug molecules [14], proteins [15], radionuclides [16], or copper(II) [17], cadmium(II) [17] and lead(II) [17] from aqueous solutions.

There are already many reports of silica-organic hybrids materials [18,19]. These have been prepared either through co-condensation reactions involving mixtures of silanes, non-covalent derivatisation, or covalent surface functionalization reactions. The two latter approaches are applicable to commercially available pre-prepared silicas so are significantly more convenient on scale. Non-covalent derivitisation is a green pathway to materials, but as sorbents are used in an aqueous environment there is a high chance of product degradation over successive washes. Covalent functionalization leads to robust, cycle-able materials, so the slightly more involved synthetic pathways are well justified.

Here, we have prepared a silica material with glycine functionalities covalently attached to the surface of commercially available silica gel particles (SiO₂-Gly). Glycine is a bidentate N,O-

chelating ligand with a particularly high affinity for first-row transition metals. Cobalt and nickel ions are valuable components of e-waste [20–23], and both are toxic to human health and the natural environment [24,25]. This SiO₂-Gly hybrid is a highly efficient sorbent for cobalt(II) and nickel(II) recovery. SiO₂-Gly and its sorption mechanism has been studied by a gamut of techniques including TGA, FTIR, visible, RAMAN and ¹H NMR spectroscopy, as well as solution phase sorption studies. Herein, we elucidate an unusual sorption mechanism and highlight the high efficacy of this novel material.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

Silica gel (0.2-0.5 nm, 500 m²/g, triethylamine (99%), iodoacetic acid (99%), 4-(2'-pyridylazo)resorcinol (97+%, ACS), (3-aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES, 99%), sodium tetraborate (98%) and dimethylglyoxime (99+%) were obtained from Acros Organics, Belgium. Nickel(II) nitrate hexahydrate (98%), cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate (98%), murexide and calcium acetate hydrate (99.0%, ACS) were obtained from Alfa Aesar, USA. Ethanol absolute, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) disodium salt (0.1 M, factor 0.998-1.002), sodium chloride (min. 99.8%), hydrochloric acid (37%), sulfuric acid (95%), nitric acid (65%) and ammonia (25%) were obtained from VWR, USA. Sodium hydroxide (98-100.5%) and toluene (≥99.7%) were obtained from Honeywell, USA. Iodine solution (0.05 M) was obtained from Merck, USA. Potassium bromide (≥99.5%) was obtained from Honeywell Fluka, USA.

2.2. Synthesis of Glycine functionalized silica (SiO₂-Gly)

Covalent grafting of glycine moieties to silica gel was accomplished by a two-step synthesis. At first, silica gel was modified by treatment with APTES according to the technique described by Tertykh and Belyakova (1991) [26,27]. Concentration of aminopropyl groups on the silica surface was determined by acid-base titration and was equal to 0.67 mmol·g⁻¹. 6 g of aminopropyl-contained silica gel (SiO₂-NH₂) was dried at 50°C overnight in order to remove physically adsorbed water. Dried SiO₂-NH₂ was placed inside a three-neck flask and suspended in 40 mL of ethanol. 7.76 mL of triethylamine and 10 mL of 7.428 g of iodoacetic acid solution in 10 mL of ethanol were added dropwise. The mixture was heated to reflux and stirred magnetically for 3 h. After cooling, the product was obtained by filtration. It was washed with ethanol (2x 25 mL) and deionised water (2x 25 mL). Finally, the washed sorbent was dried overnight at 50°C to give SiO₂-Gly (5.8 g, 97 %).

2.3. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

The thermal analysis was performed on a Perkin Elmer TGA 7, USA. The analysis was performed in dynamic atmosphere of synthetic air and the following operational conditions were applied: heating rate of $10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, temperature range of 30 – 850 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and sample mass of 2.5 mg.

2.4. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

For the collection of high temperature FTIR spectra, the Varian 610-IR FTIR spectrometer (USA) was fitted with a heating stage. Spectra were collected as reflectance measurements using the IR microscope interface and a mercury-cadmium-telluride (MCT) detector. The reported spectra were collected by focusing the optics on the edges of SiO_2 -Gly particles, and were collected over 500 scans at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

2.5. The pH of point zero charge (pH_{pzc})

Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms were recorded to determine the specific surface area and to calculate pore size distribution for silica gel and SiO_2 -Gly. A Micromeritics ASAP 2020, USA, instrument was used. Prior to the analysis, the samples were outgassed at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) surface area was calculated using the following equation:

$$\frac{x}{V(1-x)} = \frac{1}{V_m \cdot c_{\text{BET}}} + \frac{x \cdot (c_{\text{BET}} - 1)}{V_m \cdot c_{\text{BET}}} \quad (1)$$

V is the volume of adsorbed molecules, V_m is the monolayer volume, c_{BET} is the BET constant, and x is the relative pressure (p/p_0) [28]. Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method was used to estimate the pore size distribution using Kelvin equation:

$$\frac{\ln p}{p_0} = \frac{2\gamma V_m}{rRT} \quad (2)$$

p/p_0 is the relative pressure, γ is the surface tension of adsorbate, V_m is the molar volume of the liquid, R is universal gas constant, r is the radius of the meniscus formed in the mesopore and T is the temperature [29,30].

2.6. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The SEM micrographs were taken using JEOL JSM-7000F scanning electron microscope, Japan, for the SiO_2 -Gly material and LEO 1430VP, Carl Zeiss, Germany for pure silica gel. The samples were coated with a gold layer sputtered with a JEOL JFC-1200 Fine Ciater, Japan. Carbon tape was used as a support.

2.7. Carboxyl group titration

The concentration of carboxyl groups in the synthesized SiO₂-Gly sorbent was investigated by complexometric titration as described by Frasci et al. (2002) [31]. SiO₂-Gly was weighed into a flask, and 100 mL of 0.1 M calcium acetate solution was added. The mixture was shaken overnight, and then filtered. 1 mL of the solution was transferred to a beaker, and then 20 mL of deionised water and 2 mg of murexide as metalchromic indicator were added. 0.1 M sodium hydroxide solution was added to adjust the pH of the solution to 12. This solution was stirred magnetically, and titrated against 0.1 M Na₂H₂EDTA until a colour change was observed. Each measurement was repeated three times, to obtain the mean value of carboxyl group content in the sorbent. To estimate carboxyl group content, following equation was used:

$$C_{COOH} = \frac{(V_{blank} - V_{sample}) \cdot C \cdot f}{m} \quad (3)$$

where C_{COOH} is the concentration of carboxyl groups (mmol·g⁻¹), V_{blank} is the consumption of titrating agent (EDTA) for blank 0.1M calcium acetate solution (mL), V_{sample} is consumption of titrating agent (EDTA) for the sample (mL), C is the concentration of the titrating agent (M), f is the factor of the titrating agent, and m is the weight of sorbent (g) [31].

2.8. Solid state Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectroscopy (NMR)

Solid-state ¹H MAS NMR spectra were collected at the magnetic field $B_0 = 14.1$ T (¹H Larmor frequency of 600.12 MHz) and MAS rate $\nu_r = 60.00$ kHz on a Bruker Avance-III spectrometer (USA) equipped with 1.3 mm MAS probehead. Acquisitions involved a rotor-synchronized, double-adiabatic spin-echo sequence with 90° 1.25 μs excitation pulse followed by two 50.0 μs tanh/tan high-power adiabatic pulses (SHAPs) with 5 MHz frequency sweep [32,33]. All pulses operated at the nutation frequency $\nu_{nut} = 200$ kHz. 128 signal transients with 5 s relaxation delay were accumulated for each spectrum. Shifts were referenced with respect to neat tetramethylsilane (TMS).

2.9. Solid state UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy

Spectra of SiO₂-Gly sorbent and SiO₂-Gly with adsorbed cobalt or nickel ions were collected using Agilent Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer (USA) in the range from 900 to 200 nm. A KBr pellet was used as a reference and the samples were ground in agate mortar before the experiment.

2.10. Batch adsorption

0.05 g of studied sorbent was weighted and placed into 100 mL flask with 25mL of cobalt(II) nitrate or nickel(II) nitrate solution. The initial concentration range for equilibrium study were 2 – 280 mg L⁻¹ and 2 – 500 mg L⁻¹ for cobalt(II) and nickel(II) ions respectively. Flasks were placed in Heidolph Unimax 1010 incubating shaker (Germany) and shaken at 180 rpm for 3 hours at 22 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C.

For the study of pH influence to adsorption efficiency, the pH of initial solutions was adjusted from 2 to 8 using 0.01 M HNO₃ and 0.01 M NH₄OH solutions. To investigate the optimal time needed for reaching an equilibrium, the studied sorbent material was suspended with metal ion solutions and shaken for 0.25 – 24 hours.

To study the influence of pH and time on adsorption, the initial concentration of metal ions was 50 mg·L⁻¹, and the samples were shaken under ambient temperature of 22 °C. Afterwards, solutions were separated from sorbent by filtration.

In all cases, the concentration of metal ions in solutions was determined by the photometrical methods [34]. Absorbance of the formed Co(II) complexes with 4-(2'-pyridylazo)resorcinol was measured at 500 nm and Ni(II) complexes with dimethylglyoxime at 470 nm, using UV-3100PC spectrophotometer (VWR, USA). Each sample was measured three times, and the absorbance determined as the mean value from three measurements. The adsorption capacity (q_e) was determined by the following equation:

$$q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_{eq})V}{m} \quad (4)$$

where C_0 and C_{eq} are respectively the initial and equilibrium Co²⁺ or Ni²⁺ concentrations (mg·L⁻¹), V is the volume of the sample (L) and m is the mass of sorbent (g). The kinetics of the adsorption process was calculated using pseudo-first and pseudo-second-order reactions equations, presented below:

Pseudo-first-order equation:

$$\log(q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - \frac{k_1 t}{2.303} \quad (5)$$

Pseudo-second-order equation:

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e} \quad (6)$$

where q_e and q_t are the amount of adsorbed metal (mg·g⁻¹) at the equilibrium time and at any instant of time t respectively, k_1 is the rate constant of the pseudo-first-order reaction (1·min⁻¹), k_2 is the rate constant of pseudo-second-order reaction (g·mg⁻¹·min⁻¹) [35,36].

In this study, Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherm models were applied. Langmuir model assumes monolayer adsorption, which means that the adsorption occurs on a homogenous surface layer with no interaction between the adsorbed molecules. The linear form of this model can be expressed as:

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{C_e}{q_0} + \frac{1}{K_L q_0} \quad (7)$$

where C_e is the equilibrium concentration of ions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), q_e is the amount of the adsorbed ions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), q_0 and K_L are the adsorption capacity ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) and the equilibrium constant ($\text{L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$) respectively. Langmuir isotherm is often expressed by separation factor R_L , which is a dimensionless constant:

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1+K_L C_0} \quad (8)$$

where C_0 is the initial concentration of adsorbate ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$).

In case of multilayer adsorption the Freundlich model is applied, especially for heterogenous systems of organic compounds or highly interactive species. This model can be expressed as:

$$\log q_e = \log K_F + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e \quad (9)$$

where K_F and n are the Freundlich constants related to the sorption capacity ($\text{L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$) and sorption intensity respectively. Temkin model was calculated according to the following equation:

$$C_s = \frac{RT}{b_T} \ln(K_T) + \frac{RT}{b_T} \ln C_e \quad (10)$$

where C_s is the concentration of metal in solid phase ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), K_T is the model constant ($\text{L}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), R is the gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$), T is the absolute temperature (K) and C_e is the equilibrium concentration of a metal in aqueous phase ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) [35,37].

Additional tests using silica gel for adsorption of Co(II) and Ni(II) ions were performed having 120 mg L^{-1} of initial metal ions concentration under ambient temperature of 22°C for 3 hours.

2.11. Regeneration of sorbent after adsorption

Desorption tests for materials after adsorption were performed using three acid solutions: 0.1 M HCl, 0.1 M H_2SO_4 and 0.1 M HNO_3 . Sorbent samples with known amount of adsorbed metal were placed in the flasks and shaken for 3 hours with 25 mL of acid solutions at ambient temperature of 22°C . After that, the concentration of metals in solutions was measured.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Sorbent synthesis and characterization

SiO₂-Gly was obtained in a near quantitative yield, following a simple two step synthesis. Aminated silica was prepared by reaction of APTES with silica gel, and subsequently alkylated using monoiodoacetic acid in presence of triethylamine to give SiO₂-Gly (Scheme 1). This synthesis benefits from a rapid reaction and straightforward workup by filtration; essentially quantitative yields are achieved within 3 hours of reaction, with almost complete conversion of amine functionalities to glycine moieties demonstrated by complexometric titration (*vide infra*).

Scheme 1. Synthesis path of SiO₂-Gly material.

Table 1. Comparison of Co(II) and Ni(II) adsorption on different sorbents.

Sorbent	Adsorption capacity (mg·g ⁻¹)		Reference
	Co(II)	Ni(II)	
Hydroxyapatite	22.5	18.6	[3]
Activated carbon	50.3	140.85	[38,39]
<i>Spirulina</i>	95.9	-	[38]
Silica gel modified with ethylenimine	63.6	102.1	[40]
Palygorskite (clay)	8.88	-	[41]
Modified Laponite	21.8	-	[42]
Mesosponge γ-Al ₂ O ₃ monolith	196.07	-	[43]
Lignin	7.1-7.7	5.99	[44,45]
Hydrogel	262	-	[46]
Magnetic graphene oxide/chitosan	15.24	-	[47]

Polivynylpyrrolidone-coated magnetite nanoparticles	-	29.86	[48]
Chitosan/magnetite	-	52.55	[49]
Algae	-	181.2	[50]
Polivynyl alcohol/carbon nanotube	-	225.6	[51]
Ni(II)-ion imprinted silica gel	-	20.3	[52]
Polyamidoxime dendrimer magnetic microspheres	-	191.78	[53]
SiO₂-Gly	166.3	172.4	This work

Presence of N-butyl tethered glycine moieties on the surface of the silica in SiO₂-Gly was verified spectroscopically. FTIR spectra of SiO₂-Gly (Fig. 1) features a $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band at 1750 cm⁻¹ in addition to intense absorptions originating from silica between 1371-983 cm⁻¹, and $\delta(\text{O}-\text{H})$ bands associated with surface water present at 1650 cm⁻¹. Broadening of the absorbance between 3400-2700 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of SiO₂-Gly relative to untreated silica can be attributed to a contribution from carboxylate $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ absorptions [54,55].

Quantification of the attachment of functional groups to the silica surface was accomplished by TGA and titration methods. Titration indicated the presence of 0.67 mmol·g⁻¹ amine groups in the aminated silica precursor, and 0.63 mmol·g⁻¹ carboxylic acid groups in SiO₂-Gly, corresponding to 4.0 and 6.5% organic material by weight respectively for the two materials. TGA measurements were made of SiO₂-Gly as well as SiO₂-NH₂ and native SiO₂ for reference (Fig. 2 and Figures S1 – S5 in Electronic Supplementary Information). All materials analysed showed a small loss for water of ca. 3.5 % below 180 °C. Above this temperature, there was a mass loss associated with the loss of organic material and a small decomposition of silica. Untreated silica lost a further 3.5 % wt up to 800 °C, and SiO₂-NH₂ and SiO₂-Gly lost a further 9.9 and 12.8% wt% respectively. Assuming SiO₂ decomposition is consistent amongst the three samples and all organic material is pyrolysed, ca. 6.4 and 9.3% of the mass of SiO₂-NH₂ and SiO₂-Gly respectively is organic.

The nitrogen adsorption isotherm of SiO₂-Gly (Fig.3) indicates that the material is mesoporous. The shape of the nitrogen adsorption isotherm (Fig. 3) corresponds to the type IV of International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) classification which is characteristic of mesoporous materials [56]. The Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) surface area of the sorbent was 229.8 m²·g⁻¹ (Fig. S6 in ESI), single point adsorption total pore volume of pores less than 1460.4

Å diameter (at $p/p^\circ = 0.99$) was $0.52 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$, Barret-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) adsorption average pore size diameter (4V/A) was 7.3 nm and BJH desorption average pore size diameter (4V/A) was 6.1 nm (Fig. 4). IUPAC defines mesoporous materials as those which have pores sizes between 2-50 nm [56]. The $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ material synthesized is within that range, so is mesoporous. Taking into account the surface area, we can extrapolate that the density of N-tethered glycine moieties on the surface of $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ is $27 \text{ mmol} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$.

SEM was employed for imaging of SiO_2 (Fig. S13 in ESI) and $\text{SiO}_2\text{-COOH}$ sorbent (Fig. 5 and Fig. S14 in ESI) in secondary electron mode. Comparing images of silica gel with $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ material it can be seen that the surface functionalization by grafting -Gly groups has not changed the appearance of the silica surface significantly, suggesting a sparse distribution of the organic material.

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of SiO_2 (red trace) and $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ (black trace).

Fig. 2. Thermogravimetric analysis of SiO₂-Gly.

Fig. 3. Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms for SiO₂-Gly material.

Fig. 4. BJH curve of pore-size distribution by volume for SiO₂-Gly.

Fig. 5. SEM micrograph of SiO₂-Gly material.

Fig. 6. The pH_{pzc} of SiO_2 (red trace) and $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ (black trace).

3.2. Adsorption study

To assess the effectiveness of $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ as a sorbent for nickel and cobalt ions, we first characterised its behavior with respect to pH. Solution pH has profound effects on adsorption processes; pH influences both metal ion speciation and the character of surface interactions possible at the sorbent surface. The point zero charge (pH_{pzc}) represents the pH at which a species is neutral in solution. For SiO_2 and $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$, pH_{pzc} was found to be 5.30 and 4.25 respectively (Fig. 6). Addition of acidic glycine moieties has decreased the pH at which a negatively charged surface is present in $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ relative to native silica. This is favorable for the adsorption of positively charged ions such as cobalt and nickel.

To optimize extraction conditions for $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$, we studied its adsorption efficiency for Ni(II) and Co(II) ions in solutions of varying pH (Fig. 7 and Fig. S15). Increasing the pH of solution improves on the adsorption efficiency of both cobalt and nickel ions. The maximum removal efficiency of cobalt(II) ions was 84.7% ($22.5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) obtained at pH 8 in the presence of ammonia. The increase is less dramatic for nickel; similar adsorption efficiency was noted for pH 6-8, with a maximum efficiency at pH 7 ($21.6 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$). The adsorption of cobalt was sensitive to the choice of base used to prepare the pH 8 solution. Adjusting the pH with aqueous ammonia significantly improved the adsorption, while achieving the same pH using carbonate as the base actually decreased adsorption relative to that achieved at more acidic pH values (Figure S.16 in ESI). Cobalt amine complexes such as the prototypical $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{X}_n$ ($\text{X} = \text{halide}$, $n = 2, 3$) are readily oxidized in aqueous solution from Co(II) to Co(III), and harder Co(III) ions are likely more readily

adsorbed on silica surfaces. Nickel does not undergo similar redox chemistry in the presence of amine ligands. In general, addition of ammonia could be used to assist sorbent systems in discriminating between cobalt and nickel ions by increasing the sorption of the former. For further studies it was decided that cobalt adsorption experiments will be conducted at initial pH of 8 using ammonia as the base. Increasing pH above this value may cause undesired precipitation of cobalt ions, or dissolution of silica. For further nickel adsorptions pH 7 was chosen as the working pH [14].

With optimized pH values in hand (pH 7 for Ni and 8 for Co), batch adsorption experiments were undertaken to benchmark SiO₂-Gly against other reported sorbents. Removal efficiency of Co(II) and Ni(II) from 50 mg·L⁻¹ solutions are shown on Fig. S17 in ESI. Fast adsorption was observed for Co(II) ions, 91.5% was adsorbed during the first 30 minutes of incubation. Equilibrium was reached for Ni(II) ions after 3 hours of contact. The removal efficiency for nickel(II) ions increased from 65.1% to 82.5% during first 3 hours, and was constant after that time. Parameters obtained from fitting the experimental data to kinetic models are presented in Table 2. The capacity at equilibrium and adsorption rate for pseudo-first order kinetic model can be calculated from the slope and intercept of $\log(q_e - q_t)$ vs t plot (Fig. S18 in ESI). It was found that the calculated capacities at equilibrium for both metals do not match with experimental values. Additionally, the correlation coefficient (R^2) in both cases is very low: 0.527 and 0.258 for Co(II) and Ni(II) respectively, which means that the adsorption kinetics do not fit the pseudo-first order reaction. To estimate pseudo-second order kinetic parameters, the plot t/q_t vs t was made (Fig. 8). For both elements the relationship is linear, and the k_2 constant and capacity at the equilibrium were calculated from the intercept and the slope of the plot t/q_t vs t . Calculated equilibrium capacities for Co(II) and Ni(II) ions are close to the experimental values. The correlation coefficient in both cases is very high (close to 1.0). Due to the similarity in calculated and experimental equilibrium capacities and high R^2 coefficient values for both systems, it can be concluded that pseudo-second order kinetic models are a suitable kinetic description of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) adsorption on SiO₂-Gly.

The study regarding investigation of influence of initial metal ion concentration to adsorption efficiency was performed for 3 hours. It was found that adsorption capacity of SiO₂-Gly decreases with increasing of temperature from 22 °C to 60 °C in case of cobalt(II) ions but for nickel(II) ions the opposite is true, and less efficient absorption is noted at higher temperature (Fig. 9a and b). The highest adsorption capacity of Co(II) ions was 166.3 mg·g⁻¹ (at pH 8) and for nickel(II) ions the maximum capacity of 172.4 mg·g⁻¹ (at pH 7) was achieved. This value is very competitive with various literature sorbents reported (Table 1). Previous studies have reported upon cobalt(II)

adsorption on hydroxyapatite [3], activated carbon [24,38], silica gel modified with ethylenimine [40], clay [41,42], mesosponge γ -Al₂O₃ monolith [43], lignin [44], hydrogel [46], graphene [57] or hybrid materials [47,58]. Adsorption of nickel ions was also performed on many sorbents such as hydroxyapatite [3], carbon nanotubes [7], activated carbon [39], silica gel modified with ethylenimine [40], lignin [45], magnetite nanoparticles [48], chitosan/magnetite material [49], algae[50], Bi₂Se₃ surface [59] and polymers [60] or hybrid materials [51–53,61]. Of these materials, only an organic functionalized mesosponge γ -Al₂O₃ monolith [43] exceeds the sorption capacity achieved for SiO₂-Gly. This material requires a bespoke synthesis of the underlying nanostructured alumina material prior to organic functionalization, so may be more challenging to produce on scale than SiO₂-Gly.

Fig. 7. Effect of initial pH on adsorption of Co(II) and Ni(II).

Fig. 8. Pseudo-second order plot for Co(II) and Ni(II) adsorption on SiO₂-Gly.

Table 2. Kinetic parameters for the adsorption of Co(II) and Ni(II) ions on SiO₂-Gly.

Kinetic model	Parameter	Co(II)	Ni(II)
Pseudo-first order	$q_{e, exp} (mg \cdot g^{-1})$	31.56	20.71
	$q_{e, cal} (mg \cdot g^{-1})$	4.96	1.63
	$k_1 (1 \cdot min^{-1})$	0.0942	0.1018
	R^2	0.527	0.258
Pseudo-second order	$q_{e, exp} (mg \cdot g^{-1})$	31.56	20.71
	$q_{e, cal} (mg \cdot g^{-1})$	29.32	20.53
	$k_2 (g \cdot mg^{-1} \cdot min^{-1})$	0.0035	0.0089
	R^2	0.9994	0.9999

In this study, Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherm models were applied (Figs. S19 to S24 in ESI). It was found that Freundlich isotherm model fits well to the experimental data obtained for both systems. The correlation coefficient for both system for all isotherms is the highest (0.8904 - 0.9714 and 0.9796 - 0.9924 for Co(II) and Ni(II) adsorption, respectively). Freundlich model indicates that the adsorption process occur on a heterogeneous surface. The Freundlich isotherm parameters n and K_F are relatively similar between isotherms at different temperatures for both systems. The Freundlich isotherm model is the most suitable in both cases due to higher values of correlation coefficient for this model than for Langmuir and Temkin models. Correlation coefficient for the Temkin model is the lowest among other isotherm models in both

cases for all isotherms, so it is not applicable to sorption kinetics at SiO₂-Gly [37,56]. The capacity of pure silica was analysed under the same conditions, and found to be 21.03 mg·g⁻¹ for Co(II) and 8.79 mg·g⁻¹ Ni(II) which is an order of magnitude lower to the capacity of SiO₂-Gly, highlighting the value of organic decoration upon the silica surface.

In order to determine if metals can be recovered from SiO₂-Gly, desorption tests were performed on loaded silica using 0.1 M washing solutions of hydrochloric, sulfuric and nitric acids. The highest desorption efficiency for cobalt ions was obtained using 0.1 M HCl, where 75.9 % of adsorbed cobalt was recovered. Desorption efficiency using 0.1M H₂SO₄ solution reached 60.2 % and desorption efficiency using 0.1 M HNO₃ reached only 12.8 % for cobalt ions. Nickel ions recovery was slightly less effective, we achieved 63.2 % recovery after washing with 0.1 M hydrochloric acid solution. Sulfuric acid and nitric acid were comparably inferior; washing with 0.1 M H₂SO₄ and 0.1 M HNO₃ gave a desorption efficiency of 13.5 % and 11.4 % respectively.

Chosen sorbents after adsorption were analyzed by thermogravimetric method and compared to the result obtained for pure sorbent (Fig. 10). Conditions of this analysis were maintained as it was performed for pure sorbent. It can be seen that the weight loss of all three materials is similar and rather constant up to 300°C. Above this temperature, materials with adsorbed metals indicated lower decomposition rate than pure sorbent, and at the temperature of 850°C their weight loss is almost the same, achieving values of 13.4% and 13.2% for sorbents containing Co(II) and Ni(II) respectively. Comparing these values with the weight loss of pure sorbent (16.3%), it can be concluded that the metals are present on the surface of the sorbent. If we consider the experimental data for metals adsorbed on the surface, the calculated mass difference between pure sorbent and sorbent after adsorption at the point of 850°C for cobalt(II) would be 8.1% and 17.5% for nickel(II). The difference between calculated and experimental values can be explained by the non-equal distribution of metal ions onto sorbent surface.

Fig. 9. Adsorption isotherms of: (a) Co(II) ions and (b) Ni(II) ions on SiO₂-Gly material.

Table 3. Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherm models parameters for Co(II) adsorption on SiO₂-Gly.

Isotherm model	Parameter	Isotherm 22°C	Isotherm 40°C	Isotherm 60°C
Langmuir	q_0 (mg·g ⁻¹)	17.86	7.81	68.49
	K_L (L·mg ⁻¹)	1.357	1.877	0.424
	R_L	0.0523	0.0612	0.1873
	R^2	0.8815	0.8987	0.9788
Freundlich	K_F (L·mg ⁻¹)	20.02	8.07	14.28
	n	1.743	1.209	1.764
	R^2	0.9714	0.9308	0.8904
Temkin	b_T (J·mol ⁻¹)	125.04	275.96	288.42
	K_T (L·g ⁻¹)	15.93	15.03	16.71
	R^2	0.802	0.9127	0.9422

Table 4. Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherm models parameters for Ni(II) adsorption on SiO₂-Gly.

Isotherm model	Parameter	Isotherm 22°C	Isotherm 40°C	Isotherm 60°C
Langmuir	q_0 (mg·g ⁻¹)	9.71	144.93	172.41
	K_L (L·mg ⁻¹)	0.501	0.028	0.032
	R_L	0.1017	0.4147	0.0464
	R^2	0.9026	0.834	0.9456
Freundlich	K_F (L·mg ⁻¹)	5.093	5.084	6.129

	n	1.561	1.446	1.455
	R^2	0.9796	0.9924	0.9814
	b_T ($\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)	206.02	159.69	125.64
Temkin	K_T ($\text{L}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)	3.081	1.047	2.201
	R^2	0.8246	0.6943	0.8096

Fig. 10. TGA results of SiO_2 -Gly sorbent (black trace) with adsorbed Co(II) (red trace) and Ni(II) (blue trace) ions.

3.3. Mechanistic aspects

From our sorption studies, it is clear that the sorption capacity of SiO_2 -Gly for cobalt or nickel ions is more than threefold higher than the concentration of organic ligands on the silica surface. To understand the nature of the interactions between the metal and silica particles, and rationalize how an excess of metal can be present relative to the organic chelators, we have undertaken a spectroscopic study to compare ion loaded SiO_2 -Gly to the native material in the solid state. In Fig. 11, the solid-state ^1H MAS NMR spectra of the native adsorbent material and SiO_2 -Gly loaded with Co ions are presented. A key feature of the spectrum obtained of SiO_2 -Gly is a peak at 1 ppm corresponding to Si-OH groups. Further signals arise in the range of 3-6 ppm, and are assigned to various proton environments of the H_2O molecules adsorbed to the surface. Due to the intensity of water and silanol signals in the sample, no spectral features could be confidently assigned to the organic moiety. After treatment with cobalt ions, the spectra is broadened somewhat due to the paramagnetism of the adsorbed ions. A notable difference in the two spectra is that the signal corresponding to Si-OH groups is significantly weakened in the spectrum of SiO_2 -

Gly/Co, implicating electrostatic interaction between -SiO^- and $(\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_n)^{2+}$ or hydrogen bonds between silanols and ligands coordinated to the cobalt as a key interaction between metal and sorbent in the resting state.

High temperature FTIR spectra for SiO_2 -Gly sorbent after adsorption of cobalt and nickel ions was compared to the sorbent before adsorption (Fig. 12 and Fig. S25 in ESI). The spectra were collected at 80 °C to decrease the contribution of surface water to the absorbance signals. Due to the very high concentration of silica relative to organic material, contributions from silica dominate. Bands associated with silica are intensely absorbing below 1300 cm^{-1} , and $\nu(\text{Si-O})$ overtone bands appear centered at 1981 cm^{-1} and 1868 cm^{-1} [62]. The $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C=O})$ band for SiO_2 -Gly is observed at 1751 cm^{-1} . This value is characteristic of free glycine carbonyls which are not hydrogen bonding [63]. In the spectra of SiO_2 -Gly loaded with a threefold excess of Co(II) or Ni(II) ions relative to -Gly, there is no change in this band. This indicates that the loaded sorbent featured glycine moieties that are not interacting with metal complexes; no hydrogen bonding or direct complexation is evident, as both would lead to weakening of the C=O bond and a corresponding red-shift in the spectrum. Given that silica surface water is present at 1628 cm^{-1} , the same region where symmetric carboxylate bands would be expected to appear, we cannot totally rule out the possibility of some deprotonated glycine moieties contributing to binding in the solid state. However, the increase of signal intensity at 1600 cm^{-1} for material after adsorption is clearly observed.

After absorption of cobalt(II) or nickel(II) ions, the colorless SiO_2 -Gly beads take on a mauve or green tinge due to the presence of adsorbed metal ions. To probe this effect, the UV-Vis-NIR spectrum of as synthesized SiO_2 -Gly was compared with spectra collected from SiO_2 -Gly loaded with cobalt or nickel ions (Fig. 13). All spectra featured a broad band between 200 to 450 nm corresponding to adsorption by silica [64]. In the sample incubated with cobalt, an additional adsorption band was present between 500-700 nm. This is characteristic of metal-to-ligand charge transfers in cobalt complexes [65–68]. For the material with adsorbed Ni(II) no similar bands were observed, possibly due to the low concentration of adsorbed Ni(II) ions.

Fig. 11. Solid state ^1H NMR spectra for $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ material before (black trace) and after (red trace) adsorption of cobalt ions.

Fig 12. FTIR spectra of $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ sorbent before (black trace) and after adsorption of Co(II) (red trace) and Ni(II) (purple trace) ions.

Fig. 13. UV-Vis-NIR spectra for SiO₂-Gly material before (black trace) and after (red trace) adsorption of cobalt ions.

From the above spectral information, we can summarize that when SiO₂-Gly is loaded with cobalt or nickel ions, ion adsorption could involve interactions between metal complexes and deprotonated silanol groups or organic glycine substituents. Data obtained from application of Freundlich isotherm model is also indicative of adsorption onto a heterogeneous surface [37] (*vide supra*), confirming that adsorption *in solution* involves a several mechanisms. Installation of the organic substituents on the surface nonetheless results a sorbent with a tenfold improvement in capacity for metal ion sorption relative to unmodified silica, so it is of interest to rationalize all possible the adsorption mechanism.

Hydrophilic silica surfaces in contact with aqueous environments are coated with a layer of water molecules [69], which may present a kinetic barrier to the approach of metal ions. We postulated that introduction of organic functionalities may help to facilitate metal binding to silica by either i. disrupting the water layer on the surface of the silica, and/or ii. chelation site nearby the silica surface, (iii) improving the access of outer sphere complex to deprotonated silanolate or carboxyl groups [70]. The pH_{pzc} was decreased after pure silica modification by glycine, which confirms that some part of deprotonated carboxyl groups is available and could be involved into metal complexes binding.

The calculations of equilibria constants of complexing reactions on the surface were reported in [71]. It was found that the most real scenario includes creation of set of monodentate complexes

(for Co(II): $\lg K = -4.76$; for Ni(II): $\lg K = -4.96$) and hydroxocomplexes on the surface (for Co(II): $\lg K = -13.45$; for Ni(II): $\lg K = -13.72$). However, the possibility of metal bonding through two silanolate groups as bidentate hydrocomplexes could not be excluded [71]. The comparison of stability constants of surface monodentate and hydroxocomplexes led to evaluation of the equilibrium constant of hydrolysis reaction of adsorbed metal ion on the surface:

Obtained values showed that the hydrolysis of adsorbent metal ions on the surface is more probable than hydrolysis of aqua complexes in the solution:

Therefore, the formation of monodentate and hydroxyl complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) on silanolate groups is more favorable than bidentate, and rapid hydrolysis of adsorbed metal ions starts at lower pH than in the solution. Pure silica indicated much lower sorption capacity towards selected ions, which means that the adsorption through Si-OH groups is not favorable in that case. Basing on the aforementioned, electrostatic interaction of metal complexes to deprotonated silanolate groups and to the part of protonated carboxyl groups is the most probable sorption mechanism (Fig. 14). Relatively high desorption of metal ions from the surface can be additional conformation, as silanolate groups, due to much weaker bonding forces, do not enter the inner sphere of complexes and therefore it is easier to remove cobalt and nickel from the surface by changing the pH. This is in line with the results of desorption study: 75 and 63 % of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) respectively, that could successfully be leached from the sorbent's surface at low pH. The high concentration of metal complexes after adsorption on SiO₂-Gly material could also indicate multilayer adsorption [72], hence the formation of hydroxy bridges between complexes is also suggested as one of the possible bonding mechanisms of Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes [17,46,73–75].

Fig. 14. Proposed mechanism of metal ion sorption in SiO₂-Gly. [M] = metal aqua or amine complex. During stage I, metal adsorption is blocked by surface water, but approach to the carboxylate moiety is facile. In stage II, coordination to Gly places the metal close to the silica surface. In stage III, after diffusion of water away from the surface, [M] can move to the dense anionic charges (A, B); different types of inner sphere complexes of transition metal ions on the surface of silica: bidentate, monodentate or hydroxocomplex (C).

4. Conclusions

This work was focused on synthesis and characterization of SiO₂-Gly, an inorganic-organic hybrid sorbent. This material is an efficient sorbent for Co(II) and Ni(II) ions in aqueous solutions. The reasonably green, high yielding synthesis of this material in two steps from commercial silica gel is indicative of its suitability for large scale production.

Characterisation of SiO₂-Gly indicated that it is a mesoporous material, decorated with 0.63 mmol·g⁻¹ (or 27 mmol·cm⁻²) N-glycine moieties, attached to the silica surface through a butyl

chain. SEM micrographs showed minimal change to the silica surface after coating, corroborating a thin, well distributed surface layer of organic groups. The pH_{pzc} of $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ was found to be 4.25, indicating that the material has a negative surface charge above this pH, and so should be able to attract positively charged metal cations.

An adsorption study was conducted to find optimal conditions for cobalt and nickel ion extraction using $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$. The optimal pH value for adsorption of Co(II) and Ni(II) ions is 8.0 and 7.0 respectively, and addition of ammonia significantly improved Co(II) adsorption. Kinetic data of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) ions adsorption indicated that the process follows pseudo-second order model, indicating adsorption onto a heterogeneous surface. Adsorption isotherms in both cases were described using Freundlich model. The maximum adsorption capacities are $166.3 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for Co ions and $172.4 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for Ni ions, which is comparable with the best reported sorbents in the literature. High removal efficiency for both metals was obtained using 0.1 M HCl solution, 75.9 and 63.2% for Co(II) and Ni(II) ions respectively could be recovered. In light of the cheap preparation of this material, the high capacity achieved places $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ as a promising candidate for applications in recycling.

To understand the strong sorption performance of $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$, a mechanistic study of the loaded sorbent material was undertaken. FTIR and solid state ^1H NMR spectra indicated that the electrostatic interaction of metal complexes to dissociated silanolate groups or to part of negatively charged carboxyl groups is the main mechanism of the adsorption. Presently, our lab is continuing work on $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Gly}$ and other similar green sorbents, with a focus on metal recovery from E-waste leachates, and these developments will be disclosed in due course.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jędrzej Piątek: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Caspar de Bruin-Dickason:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Aleksander Jaworski:** Formal analysis. **Tetyana Budnyak:** Methodology, Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Adam Slabon:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Acknowledgments

This work was financially supported by the Stiftelsen Olle Engkvists (Project Nr. 198-0329).

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships which have, or could be perceived to have, influenced the work reported in this article.

References

- [1] C.O. Onwosi, V.C. Igbokwe, T.N. Nwagu, J.N. Odimba, C.O. Nwuche, E-Waste Management from Macroscopic to Microscopic Scale, in: A. Khan, Inamuddin, A.M. Asiri (Eds.), *E-Waste Recycl. Manag. Present Scenar. Environ. Issues*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2020: pp. 143–157. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-14184-4_8.
- [2] K. Grant, F.C. Goldizen, P.D. Sly, M.N. Brune, M. Neira, M. van den Berg, R.E. Norman, Health consequences of exposure to e-waste: A systematic review, *Lancet Glob. Heal.* 1 (2013) e350–e361. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(13\)70101-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(13)70101-3).
- [3] M. Ferri, S. Campisi, A. Gervasini, Nickel and cobalt adsorption on hydroxyapatite: a study for the demetalation of electronic industrial wastewaters, *Adsorption* (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10450-019-00066-w>.
- [4] N.K. Srivastava, C.B. Majumder, Novel biofiltration methods for the treatment of heavy metals from industrial wastewater, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 151 (2008) 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2007.09.101>.
- [5] H. Chen, X. Qu, N. Liu, S. Wang, X. Chen, S. Liu, Study of the adsorption process of heavy metals cations on Kraft lignin, *Chem. Eng. Res. Des.* 139 (2018) 248–258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cherd.2018.09.028>.
- [6] A. Celik, A. Demirbaş, Removal of heavy metal ions from aqueous solutions via adsorption onto modified lignin from pulping wastes, *Energy Sources.* 27 (2005) 1167–1177. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00908310490479583>.
- [7] Ihsanullah, A. Abbas, A.M. Al-Amer, T. Laoui, M.J. Al-Marri, M.S. Nasser, M. Khraisheh, M.A. Atieh, Heavy metal removal from aqueous solution by advanced carbon nanotubes: Critical review of adsorption applications, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 157 (2016) 141–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2015.11.039>.
- [8] F. Fu, Q. Wang, Removal of heavy metal ions from wastewaters: A review, *J. Environ. Manage.* 92 (2011) 407–418. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2010.11.011>.
- [9] C. Manfredi, R. Mozzillo, S. Volino, M. Trifuoggi, A. Giarra, V. Gargiulo, M. Alfé, On the modeling of heavy metals and rare earth elements adsorption on colloidal carbon-based nanoparticles, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 505 (2020) 144264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2019.144264>.
- [10] M. Minamisawa, H. Minamisawa, S. Yoshida, N. Takai, Characterization of adsorption gels prepared from plant biomaterials, *Green Chem.* 7 (2005) 595–601. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b501946j>.

- [11] A. Muñoz García, A.J. Hunt, V.L. Budarin, H.L. Parker, P.S. Shuttleworth, G.J. Ellis, J.H. Clark, Starch-derived carbonaceous mesoporous materials (Starbon®) for the selective adsorption and recovery of critical metals, *Green Chem.* 17 (2015) 2146–2149. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5gc00154d>.
- [12] S. Mincke, T.G. Asere, I. Verheye, K. Folens, F. Vanden Bussche, L. Lapeire, K. Verbeken, P. Van Der Voort, D.A. Tessema, F. Fufa, G. Du Laing, C. V. Stevens, Functionalized chitosan adsorbents allow recovery of palladium and platinum from acidic aqueous solutions, *Green Chem.* 21 (2019) 2295–2306. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9gc00166b>.
- [13] P. Anastas, N. Eghbali, Green chemistry: Principles and practice, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 39 (2010) 301–312. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b918763b>.
- [14] L. Han, O. Terasaki, S. Che, Carboxylic group functionalized ordered mesoporous silicas, *J. Mater. Chem.* 21 (2011) 11033–11039. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c1jm10561b>.
- [15] M. Barczak, Functionalization of mesoporous silica surface with carboxylic groups by Meldrum's acid and its application for sorption of proteins, *J. Porous Mater.* 26 (2019) 291–300. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10934-018-0655-7>.
- [16] C. Zhang, X. Li, Z. Jiang, Y. Zhang, T. Wen, M. Fang, X. Tan, A. Alsaedi, T. Hayat, X. Wang, Selective Immobilization of Highly Valent Radionuclides by Carboxyl Functionalized Mesoporous Silica Microspheres: Batch, XPS, and EXAFS Analyses, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 6 (2018) 15644–15652. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.8b04146>.
- [17] Y. Li, J. He, K. Zhang, T. Liu, Y. Hu, X. Chen, C. Wang, X. Huang, L. Kong, J. Liu, Super rapid removal of copper, cadmium and lead ions from water by NTA-silica gel, *RSC Adv.* 9 (2019) 397–407. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8RA08638A>.
- [18] P. Majewski, T. Albrecht, S. Weber, COOH-functionalisation of silica particles, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 257 (2011) 9282–9286. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2011.04.145>.
- [19] W. Yantasee, R.D. Rutledge, W. Chouyyok, V. Sukwarotwat, G. Orr, C.L. Warner, M.G. Warner, G.E. Fryxell, R.J. Wiacek, C. Timchalk, R.S. Addleman, Functionalized nanoporous silica for the removal of heavy metals from biological systems: Adsorption and application, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces.* 2 (2010) 2749–2758. <https://doi.org/10.1021/am100616b>.
- [20] D. Quintero-Almanza, Z. Gamiño-Arroyo, L.E. Sánchez-Cadena, F.I. Gómez-Castro, A.R. Uribe-Ramírez, A.F. Aguilera-Alvarado, L.M.O. Carmona, Recovery of cobalt from spent lithium-ion mobile phone batteries using liquid–liquid extraction, *Batteries.* 5 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries5020044>.

- [21] L. Huiqiao, W. Yonggang, N. Haitao, L. Haimei, Z. Haoshen, Rechargeable Ni-Li battery integrated aqueous/nonaqueous system, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 131 (2009) 15098–15099. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja906529g>.
- [22] Y. Du, S. Zhao, J. Li, H. Chen, C. Xu, W. Zhang, P. Li, H. Jin, Y. Zhang, J. Zhang, Rechargeable High-Capacity Aluminum-Nickel Batteries, *ChemistrySelect.* 4 (2019) 13191–13197. <https://doi.org/10.1002/slct.201903842>.
- [23] E. Hsu, K. Barmak, A.C. West, A.H.A. Park, Advancements in the treatment and processing of electronic waste with sustainability: A review of metal extraction and recovery technologies, *Green Chem.* 21 (2019) 919–936. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c8gc03688h>.
- [24] E. Demirbaş, Adsorption of cobalt(II) ions from aqueous solution onto activated carbon prepared from hazelnut shells, *Adsorpt. Sci. Technol.* 21 (2003) 951–963. <https://doi.org/10.1260/02636170360744380>.
- [25] A. for T.S. and D.R. U.S. Department of Health & Human Services, Toxicology Profile for Nickel, *Toxicol. Profile Nickel.* (2005) 1–397. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2013/286524>.
- [26] V. A. Tertykh and L. A. Belyakova, Chemical reactions involving silica surface, Kiev: Naukova Dumka (1991), 141-175.
- [27] R. Kishor, A.K. Ghoshal, APTES grafted ordered mesoporous silica KIT-6 for CO₂ adsorption, *Chem. Eng. J.* 262 (2015) 882–890. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2014.10.039>.
- [28] M. Naderi, Surface Area: Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET), *Prog. Filtr. Sep.* (2015) 585–608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-384746-1.00014-8>.
- [29] R. Bardestani, G.S. Patience, S. Kaliaguine, Experimental methods in chemical engineering: specific surface area and pore size distribution measurements—BET, BJH, and DFT, *Can. J. Chem. Eng.* 97 (2019) 2781–2791. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cjce.23632>.
- [30] E.P. Barrett, L.G. Joyner, P.P. Halenda, The Determination of Pore Volume and Area Distributions in Porous Substances. I. Computations from Nitrogen Isotherms, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 73 (1951) 373–380. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja01145a126>.
- [31] L. Fras, K. Stana-Kleinschek, Quantitative determination of carboxyl groups in cellulose by complexometric titration, *Lenzinger* (2002) 80–88. http://www.lenzinger.com/fileadmin/template/pdf/konzern/lenzinger_berichte/ausgabe_81_2002/LB_2002_Fras_16_ev.pdf.
- [32] T.L. Hwang, P.C.M. Van Zijl, M. Garwood, Fast Broadband Inversion by Adiabatic Pulses, *J. Magn. Reson.* 133 (1998) 200–203. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jmre.1998.1441>.

- [33] G. Kervern, G. Pintacuda, L. Emsley, Fast adiabatic pulses for solid-state NMR of paramagnetic systems, *Chem. Phys. Lett.* 435 (2007) 157–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cplett.2006.12.056>.
- [34] M. Marchenko, *Photometric Detection of Traces of Elements*, Moscow: MIR (1971).
- [35] T.M. Budnyak, S. Aminzadeh, I. V. Pylypchuk, D. Sternik, V.A. Tertykh, M.E. Lindström, O. Sevastyanova, Methylene Blue dye sorption by hybrid materials from technical lignins, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 6 (2018) 4997–5007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2018.07.041>.
- [36] J.P. Simonin, On the comparison of pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order rate laws in the modeling of adsorption kinetics, *Chem. Eng. J.* 300 (2016) 254–263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2016.04.079>.
- [37] N. Ayawei, A.N. Ebelegi, D. Wankasi, Modelling and Interpretation of Adsorption Isotherms, *J. Chem.* 2017 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/3039817>.
- [38] E.C. Peres, J.M. Cunha, G.F. Dortzbacher, F.A. Pavan, É.C. Lima, E.L. Foletto, G.L. Dotto, Treatment of leachates containing cobalt by adsorption on *Spirulina* sp. and activated charcoal, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 6 (2018) 677–685. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2017.12.060>.
- [39] K. Anoop Krishnan, K.G. Sreejalekshmi, R.S. Baiju, Nickel(II) adsorption onto biomass based activated carbon obtained from sugarcane bagasse pith, *Bioresour. Technol.* 102 (2011) 10239–10247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2011.08.069>.
- [40] A.G.S. Prado, L.N.H. Arakaki, C. Airoidi, Adsorption and separation of cations on silica gel chemically modified by homogeneous and heterogeneous routes with the ethylenimine anchored on thiol modified silica gel, *Green Chem.* 4 (2002) 42–46. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b108749e>.
- [41] M. He, Y. Zhu, Y. Yang, B. Han, Y. Zhang, Adsorption of cobalt(II) ions from aqueous solutions by palygorskite, *Appl. Clay Sci.* 54 (2011) 292–296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2011.09.013>.
- [42] T. Thiebault, J. Brendlé, G. Augé, L. Limousy, Zwitterionic-surfactant modified LAPONITE®s for removal of ions (Cs^+ , Sr^{2+} and Co^{2+}) from aqueous solutions as a sustainable recovery method for radionuclides from aqueous wastes, *Green Chem.* 21 (2019) 5118–5127. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9gc02243k>.
- [43] H. Gomaa, M.A. Shenashen, H. Yamaguchi, A.S. Alamoudi, S.A. El-Safty, Extraction and recovery of Co^{2+} ions from spent lithium-ion batteries using hierarchical mesosponge $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ monolith extractors, *Green Chem.* 20 (2018) 1841–1857. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7gc03673f>.

- [44] A. Demirbas, Adsorption of Co(II) and Hg(II) from water and wastewater onto modified lignin, *Energy Sources, Part A Recover. Util. Environ. Eff.* 29 (2007) 117–123. <https://doi.org/10.1080/009083190948720>.
- [45] X. Guo, S. Zhang, X. quan Shan, Adsorption of metal ions on lignin, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 151 (2008) 134–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2007.05.065>.
- [46] W. Zhang, L. Hu, S. Hu, Y. Liu, Optimized synthesis of novel hydrogel for the adsorption of copper and cobalt ions in wastewater, *RSC Adv.* 9 (2019) 16058–16068. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9ra00227h>.
- [47] S. Zhuang, J. Wang, Removal of cobalt ion from aqueous solution using magnetic graphene oxide/chitosan composite, *Environ. Prog. Sustain. Energy.* 38 (2019) S32–S41. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ep.12912>.
- [48] J. Hong, J. Xie, S. Mirshahghassemi, J. Lead, Metal (Cd, Cr, Ni, Pb) removal from environmentally relevant waters using polyvinylpyrrolidone-coated magnetite nanoparticles, *RSC Adv.* 10 (2020) 3266–3276. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9ra10104g>.
- [49] H.V. Tran, L.D. Tran, T.N. Nguyen, Preparation of chitosan/magnetite composite beads and their application for removal of Pb(II) and Ni(II) from aqueous solution, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C.* 30 (2010) 304–310. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2009.11.008>.
- [50] S. Kalyani, P. Srinivasa Rao, A. Krishnaiah, Removal of nickel (II) from aqueous solutions using marine macroalgae as the sorbing biomass, *Chemosphere.* 57 (2004) 1225–1229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2004.08.057>.
- [51] H. Wang, W. Wang, Y. Zhao, Z. Xu, L. Chen, L. Zhao, X. Tian, W. Sun, Superior adsorption of 3D nanoporous architectures for Ni(II) ions adsorption using polyvinyl alcohol as cross-linking agent and adsorption conveyor, *RSC Adv.* 8 (2018) 7899–7903. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c8ra00113h>.
- [52] H. He, Q. Gan, C. Feng, Preparation and application of Ni(ii) ion-imprinted silica gel polymer for selective separation of Ni(ii) from aqueous solution, *RSC Adv.* 7 (2017) 15102–15111. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7ra00101k>.
- [53] D. Yimin, L. Danyang, Z. Jiaqi, W. Shengyun, Z. Yi, Facile preparation of amidoxime-functionalized Fe₃O₄@SiO₂-: G -PAMAM-AO magnetic composites for enhanced adsorption of Pb(ii) and Ni(ii) from aqueous solution, *RSC Adv.* 9 (2019) 9171–9179. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9ra00128j>.
- [54] A.S. Khan, H. Khalid, Z. Sarfraz, M. Khan, J. Iqbal, N. Muhammad, M.A. Fareed, I.U. Rehman, Vibrational spectroscopy of selective dental restorative materials, *Appl. Spectrosc. Rev.* 52 (2017) 507–540. <https://doi.org/10.1080/05704928.2016.1244069>.

- [55] T.M. Budnyak, S. Aminzadeh, I. V. Pylypchuk, A. V. Riazanova, V.A. Tertykh, M.E. Lindström, O. Sevastyanova, Peculiarities of synthesis and properties of Lignin–Silica nanocomposites prepared by Sol-Gel method, *Nanomaterials*. 8 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano8110950>.
- [56] K.S.W. Sing, Reporting physisorption data for gas/solid systems, *Pure Appl. Chem.* 54 (1982) 2201–2218. <https://doi.org/10.1351/pac198254112201>.
- [57] Z. Liu, Y. guo Zhang, B. Han, Z. chao Tan, Q. hai Li, Adsorption of cobalt(III) by graphene and activated carbon, *Can. J. Chem. Eng.* 97 (2019) 940–946. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cjce.23251>.
- [58] C. Liu, D. Zhao, K. Zhang, H. Xuan, A. Alsaedi, T. Hayat, C. Chen, Fabrication of Si/Ti–based amino-functionalized hybrids and their adsorption towards cobalt(II), *J. Mol. Liq.* 289 (2019) 111051. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2019.111051>.
- [59] D.A. Pudikov, E. V. Zhizhin, G.G. Vladimirov, Nickel Adsorption on Bi₂Se₃ Surface, *Phys. Solid State*. 60 (2018) 1016–1020. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1063783418050256>.
- [60] M. Iqbal, Z. Ali, M.A. Qamar, A. Ali, F. Hussain, M. Abbas, J. Nisar, Nickel adsorption onto polyurethane ethylene and vinyl acetate sorbents, *Water Sci. Technol.* 76 (2017) 219–235. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2017.213>.
- [61] D. Yimin, L. Danyang, Z. Jiaqi, W. Shengyun, Z. Yi, Facile preparation of amidoxime-functionalized Fe₃O₄@SiO₂-: G -PAMAM-AO magnetic composites for enhanced adsorption of Pb(ii) and Ni(ii) from aqueous solution, *RSC Adv.* 9 (2019) 9171–9179. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9ra00128j>.
- [62] A.M. Efimov, V.G. Pogareva, IR absorption spectra of vitreous silica and silicate glasses: The nature of bands in the 1300 to 5000 cm⁻¹ region, *Chem. Geol.* 229 (2006) 198–217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2006.01.022>.
- [63] A. Gómez-Zavaglia, R. Fausto, Low-temperature solid-state FTIR study of glycine, sarcosine and N,N-dimethylglycine: Observation of neutral forms of simple α-amino acids in the solid state, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 5 (2003) 3154–3161. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b304888h>.
- [64] L. Bonneviot, O. Legendre, M. Kermarec, D. Olivier, M. Che, Characterization by UV-vis-NIR reflectance spectroscopy of the exchange sites of nickel on silica, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 134 (1990) 534–547. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9797\(90\)90161-G](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9797(90)90161-G).
- [65] A. Ceglia, W. Meulebroeck, K. Baert, H. Wouters, K. Nys, H. Thienpont, H. Terryn, Cobalt absorption bands for the differentiation of historical na and ca/k rich glass, *Surf. Interface Anal.* 44 (2012) 219–226. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sia.3810>.

- [66] M. Medvidović-Kosanović, A. Stanković, M. Jozanović, M. Drulak, M. Ilić, Electrochemical and UV/Vis study of L-histidine and its complexes with cobalt and nickel, *Croat. Chem. Acta.* 91 (2018) 421–426. <https://doi.org/10.5562/cca3423>.
- [67] A.M. Shalash, H.I. Abu Ali, Synthesis, crystallographic, spectroscopic studies and biological activity of new cobalt(II) complexes with bioactive mixed sulindac and nitrogen-donor ligands, *Chem. Cent. J.* 11 (2017) 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13065-017-0268-2>.
- [68] A.B.P. Lever, Charge transfer spectra of transition metal complexes, *J. Chem. Educ.* 51 (1974) 612–616. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ed051p612>.
- [69] G. Vigil, Z. Xu, S. Steinberg & J. Israelachvili, Interactions of Silica Surfaces. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 165(2), (1994) 367–385. <https://doi:10.1006/jcis.1994.1242>.
- [70] N.N. Vlasova, L.P. Golovkova, O. V. Markitan, N.G. Stukalina, Ternary surface complexes in silica- Ni^{2+} ions-2,2'-dipyridyl systems, *Colloid J.* 76 (2014) 285–291. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1061933X14020148>.
- [71] N.N. Vlasova, Complex formation of 3d transition metal cations with silanol groups of silica, *Surface.* 1 (2009) 4–13.
- [72] E. Polido Legaria, M. Samouhos, V.G. Kessler, G.A. Seisenbaeva, Toward Molecular Recognition of REEs: Comparative Analysis of Hybrid Nanoadsorbents with the Different Complexonate Ligands EDTA, DTPA, and TTHA, *Inorg. Chem.* 56 (2017) 13938–13948. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.inorgchem.7b02056>.
- [73] C.N. De Bruin-Dickason, A.G.B. Deacon, D.C.M. Forsyth, S. Hanf, A.O.B. Heilmann, A.B.R.W. Hinton, P.C. Junk, D.A.E. Somers, B.Y.Q. Tan, D.R.T. A, Synthesis and Structures of Rare Earth Complexes – New Corrosion Inhibitors *, *Aust. J. Chem.* (2017) 478–484. <https://doi.org/10.1071/CH16547> Synthesis.
- [74] E.G. Palacios, G. Juárez-López, A.J. Monhemius, Infrared spectroscopy of metal carboxylates: II. Analysis of Fe(III), Ni and Zn carboxylate solutions, *Hydrometallurgy.* 72 (2004) 139–148. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-386X\(03\)00137-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-386X(03)00137-3).
- [75] K. Nakamoto, *Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds Part B: Applications in Coordination, Organometallic and Bioorganic Chemistry*, Wiley, New Jersey, 6th edition (2009).